

In-situ Growth of WSe₂ Nanoflowers on Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene: A Multifunctional Hybrid for Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution, Lithium-Ion Batteries and Hydrogen Peroxide Electrochemical Sensing

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KEYWORDS

Tungsten diselenide, MXene, hydrogen evolution, lithium-ion batteries, electrochemical sensing

ABSTRACT

Developing efficient multifunctional materials for energy and sensing applications is challenging due to the need for high conductivity, catalytic activity, and stability. In this context, we employ a simple solvothermal method to grow WSe₂ nanoflowers in-situ onto Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene with Cl-terminations, creating WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid. The direct contact between WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂, promotes electron flow boosting conductivity and provides more electrochemical active sites, resulting in exceptional electrocatalytic activity for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), with an overpotential at -10 mA cm^{-2} as low as -0.19 V vs RHE . The optimal WSe₂-to-Ti₃C₂Cl₂ ratio was assessed through HER studies, revealing that the hybrid with a higher WSe₂ proportion exhibited enhanced electrocatalytic activity and was further explored in the other electrochemical applications. As an anode in lithium-ion batteries, the hybrid richer in WSe₂, outperforms both intact WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂, achieving an initial discharge capacity of 1255 mAh g^{-1} – almost double

that of WSe₂ and triple that of Ti₃C₂Cl₂. WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibits improved rate and cycling performance due to the enhanced conductivity while the combination of the flower-like WSe₂ directly grown on the MXene matrix contributes to volume changes during lithiation/delithiation, preventing mechanical degradation. The superior electrocatalytic activity of the hybrid was further reflected for H₂O₂ reduction, where it showed a two-fold higher response compared to WSe₂. Under optimized conditions, WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ enables amperometric determination of H₂O₂ over the concentration range 1-88 μM (R²=0.9957), with a limit of detection of 0.6 μM. All in all, the in-situ growth of WSe₂ on Ti₃C₂Cl₂ leads to a highly efficient material that integrates energy storage, conversion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electrochemistry has garnered significant attention in recent years thanks to its unique ability to combine energy storage, conversion, and sensing technologies, serving as a cost-effective alternative for environmental sustainability.¹ The performance of these electrochemical systems relies upon using materials that facilitate electron transfer and enhance the efficiency of the applications. Nevertheless, each electrochemical system has unique requirements that can differentiate the suitability of various materials. High electrical conductivity, good charge transfer kinetics, and large surface area are desirable properties of electrochemical systems.^{1,2} In contrast, good adsorption, high (electro)catalytic activity, and porosity are more controversial properties that can benefit one application and interfere with the other. Considering that, the discovery of multifunctional materials that can benefit multifold electrochemical applications is limited. The discovery of such materials is highly valuable due to their capability to address several issues at the same time. In particular, such materials can improve hydrogen production, enhance lithium-ion batteries' energy storage capacity and stability, and provide sensitive and reliable sensing for environmental monitoring, industrial safety, and public health. Electrocatalytic hydrogen production via the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) is a promising and cost-effective method for green energy conversion.^{3,4} However, noble metal-based electrocatalysts' high cost and scarcity limit their practical use.^{3,4} Similarly, while lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are widely used in electric vehicles and portable devices, their energy density and rate capabilities fall short of modern demands.^{5,6} As a result, next-generation metal-based batteries with improved capacity, stability,

and cycle life are essential. Moreover, sensing applications are vital for safety in medicine, environmental protection, and food chemistry. Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) plays a key role in biological processes and industrial uses but poses health risks at high levels, especially in food.^{7,8} Sensors using simple materials are essential for detecting H_2O_2 in environmental and biological settings. Multifunctional materials that address these needs remain rare, but their development could simplify technology and reduce costs, enabling sustainable, high-performance applications.

To this end, two-dimensional (2D) materials are attracting attention for their unique structures and adaptability in diverse technologies. Notably, MXenes and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) stand out for their exceptional electronic, optical, and chemical properties, making them promising for electrocatalysis, energy storage, and sensing applications.^{9, 10} MXenes follow the molecular formula $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$, where M is an early transition metal, A is a group 13 and 14 elements, X is carbon and/or nitrogen, and $n = 1-4$. MXenes are synthesized by selective etching of the "A" element of the corresponding MAX phase.¹¹ This results in a unique 2D material with high conductivity, tunable surface chemistry, and versatility for energy, catalysis, and sensing applications. Over the years, various etching methods have been developed to synthesize MXenes, including traditional hydrofluoric acid (HF)-based etching and, more recently, molten salt (MS).

In this regard, molten salt etching, particularly Lewis acidic molten salt (LAMS) approaches, has emerged as a promising alternative for MXene synthesis due to its ability to produce MXenes with exclusive surface terminations.¹² For example, etching Ti_3AlCl_2 MAX phases with molten CuCl_2 , FeCl_2 , or ZnCl_2 salts has yielded Cl-terminated MXenes. However, these methods are often associated with challenges such as introducing undesired surface groups during post-synthesis washing (e.g., CuCl_2 due to washing with ammonium persulfate solution)¹² or the need for inert storage conditions for highly hygroscopic salts like ZnCl_2 .¹³ CdCl_2 has also been used as a molten salt for LAMS, yielding high-quality Cl-terminated MXenes.¹³ However, its toxicity and carcinogenic risks pose serious concerns for large-scale and sustainable synthesis. We propose the use of potassium chloride (KCl) as a co-solvent to address these limitations and reduce reliance on toxic compounds like CdCl_2 . It offers practical advantages due to its low cost, wide availability, and ease of handling under ambient conditions. By combining KCl with CdCl_2 in optimized ratios, these Cl-terminated MXenes, with their well-defined surface terminations, provide an ideal

scaffold for the in-situ growth of functional nanomaterials like TMDs with the molecular formula MX_2 , where M stands for transition metal and X represents the chalcogen (S, Se, Te).¹⁴ Although Ti_3C_2 MXene has shown great promise in sensing and energy storage and conversion¹⁰ when it comes to electrocatalytic HER, it has fallen short of expectations, especially given its high electronic conductivity and success in other electrolytic systems. Despite predictions of high HER activity, Ti_3C_2 MXene has shown a significantly large overpotential in aqueous electrolytes. Specifically, its overpotential is nearly double that of Ti_4N_3 nitride MXene (0.8 V vs. 0.4 V) and is considerably higher than Mo_2C carbide MXene.¹⁵ The reason for this was recently revealed by studying the electrocatalytic HER mechanism with in situ Raman spectroscopy. The analysis of Ti_3C_2 MXene in the HER process revealed a shift in surface terminations from $-\text{O}$ to $-\text{OH}$ under acidic conditions, resulting from proton adsorption.¹³ This imbalance in protonation and deprotonation at Ti/O sites likely contributes to the high overpotential of Ti_3C_2 MXene during HER. Thus, combining Ti_3C_2 MXene with other nanomaterials such as TMDs, is rational to boost their performance.¹⁵

In this frame, tungsten diselenide (WSe_2), a representative member of the TMDs family, has shown great potential in electrocatalytic HER.^{16,17,18} When solvothermal bottom-up methods produce WSe_2 , they can provide materials with increases surface area and abundant defected sites that are highly valuable for electrocatalysis and are in high quantity and the desired polymorph. 1T (metallic) phase is more desirable than the semiconducting (2H) due to the sufficient charge transfer that helps the reaction kinetics.¹⁹ When it comes to battery technology, WSe_2 has exhibited promising results,¹⁷ although up until now, WSe_2 nanostructured anodes have been quite limited. Its layered structure promotes efficient lithium-ion diffusion owing to its relatively large interlayer spacing of 0.65 nm. Its high density of 9.32 g cm^{-3} , in turn, makes it appealing for the high volumetric energy densities required in applications like electric vehicles.²⁰ As regards sensing, WSe_2 has been involved in gas sensing,²¹ but its electroanalytical sensing capabilities remain unexplored.

In situ growth of the immobilization of 2D materials or nanoparticles supported by conductive substrates is a widely recognized concept.^{22,23} These substrates provide a structure to support the deposited material and act synergistically to enhance conductivity and charge transfer kinetics. In most electrocatalytic processes, electrical conductivity is one of the most critical factors in

achieving a good performance. High conductivity can realize very effective energy conversion by reducing the Schottky barrier in catalyst-electrolyte and catalyst-electrode interfaces, thus facilitating the path that electrons travel and increasing the efficiency of the overall reaction.²⁴ Existing studies for hybrids consisting of WSe₂ and MXene are scarce, involving high-temperature synthetic procedures,²⁵ electrostatic interactions²⁶, or via simple mixing.²⁷ These hybrids have predominantly been applied to individual applications such as HER and/or supercapacitors,^{25,28} or gas sensing.²⁶ However, to the best of our knowledge, the concept of in-situ growth of WSe₂ onto Cl-terminated Ti₃C₂MXene designed as a truly multifunctional hybrid capable of addressing HER, lithium-ion batteries, and sensing applications has not been explored. This underscores the potential of our approach in developing a versatile, multifunctional material.

In this work, we employed a straightforward solvothermal method to achieve the in-situ growth of WSe₂ nanoflowers on Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene. First, the MXene was synthesized using the LAMS approach, which combined KCl and CdCl₂ to achieve Cl-terminated surfaces. The ratios of WSe₂ to MXene were optimized based on the performance in HER in acidic medium. The hybrid material with the optimal ratio was further explored as an anode for Li-ion batteries and an electrocatalyst for the amperometric determination of H₂O₂. The materials were structurally and morphologically characterized by using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS,) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The strong interaction between the two components due to their immediate contact along with the synergetic effect between the two materials *i) enhance electron flow enabling lower overpotentials to initiate hydrogen production, ii) attain a higher initial discharge capacity with improved rate capability and cycling stability, resulting in enhanced Li-ion battery performance and iii) exhibit higher cathodic current in the presence of H₂O₂, leading to an electrochemical sensor with improved sensitivity.*

2 EXPERIMENTAL

General. Ti₃AlC₂ MAX phase was purchased from inzhou Haixin Metal Materials Co., Ltd (China). All the other chemicals, reagents, and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification.

Synthesis of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene. The Cl-terminated MXenes were synthesized using a modified version of a previously reported procedure.²⁹ Briefly, Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase (3 g) was mixed with CdCl_2 and KCl in varying molar ratios (1:6:2, 1:5:3, 1:3:5, and 1:2:6). The mixture was homogenized using a mortar and pestle and ground for 10 minutes. The resulting mixtures were pressed into pellets and placed in alumina crucibles. The reactions were conducted under an argon atmosphere (flow rate ≈ 4 mL/min) in an alumina tube at 700°C with a dwell time of 24 hours, with a controlled heating and cooling rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. After the reaction, the MXenes were recovered by dissolving residues of cadmium metal in concentrated HCl . For this, the solid products including the alumina crucible were transferred to a glass beaker, and 200 mL of HCl was added and left overnight to ensure the complete dissolution of excess reactants. The mixture was then centrifuged (3224 rcf, 5 min) and washed with deionized water until the supernatant reached a neutral pH, followed by two additional washes with methanol. Finally, the sample was vacuum-dried at 35°C for at least 12 hours, and the powder was collected for subsequent steps.

Preparation of WSe_2 . Tungsten hexacarbonyl (1 mmol) and selenium powder (2 mmol) were dissolved in 30 mL of dimethylformamide (DMF), and the resulting suspension was transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave reactor and heated at 200°C for 13 h. After the autoclave was cooled to room temperature, the resulting suspension was centrifuged at 10 000 rpm with DMF (2 times), distilled water (3 times) and methanol (3 times).

Preparation of $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene with higher WSe_2 content. Tungsten hexacarbonyl (0.5 mmol) and selenium powder (1 mmol) along with 2.5 mg of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene were dissolved in 30 mL DMF and the resulting suspension was transferred into a 50 mL teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave reactor and heated at 200°C for 13 h. After the autoclave was cooled to room temperature, the resulting suspension was centrifuged at 10 000 rpm with DMF (2 times), distilled water (3 times) and methanol (3 times). This sample is designated as w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Preparation of $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene with higher MXene content. Tungsten hexacarbonyl (0.145 mmol) and selenium powder (0.29 mmol) along with 20 mg of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene were dissolved in 30 mL DMF and the resulting suspension was transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave reactor and heated at 200°C for 13 h. After the autoclave was cooled to room temperature, the resulting suspension was centrifuged at 10 000 rpm with DMF (2 times), distilled water (3 times) and methanol (3 times). This sample is designated as m- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Microscopy techniques. The morphology of analyzed materials was investigated using SEM with a Tescan MAIA-3 Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM). EDS measurements were performed for elemental composition and mapping of elements using an 80 mm² SDD detector (Oxford Instruments) and AZtecEnergy software from Oxford Instruments. The samples were placed on a carbon conductive tape to conduct the measurements. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed using an EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS microscope (Jeol, Japan) at an acceleration voltage of 200 keV. Pictures were taken by SIS MegaView III digital camera (Soft Imaging Systems) and analyzed by AnalySIS v. 2.0 software. Elemental maps were acquired with an SDD detector X-MaxN 80 TS from Oxford Instruments (England). For sample preparation, suspensions were prepared in pure ethanol and drop-casted on a TEM grid (Cu, 200 mesh, Formvar/carbon from TED PELLA, Inc.) and dried overnight at room temperature.

XRD. X-ray powder diffraction data were collected at room temperature on Bruker D8 Discoverer (Bruker, Germany) powder diffractometer with parafocusing Bragg–Brentano geometry using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm, $U = 40$ kV, $I = 40$ mA). Data were scanned over the angular range 5–70° (2θ) with a step size of 0.019° (2θ). Data evaluation was performed in the software package EVA.

Raman spectroscopy. inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, England) in backscattering geometry with CCD detector was used for Raman spectroscopy. DPSS laser (532 nm, 50 mW) with an applied power of 5 mW and 50x magnification objective was used for the measurement. Instrument calibration was achieved with a silicon reference, which gives a peak position of 520 cm⁻¹ and a resolution of less than 1 cm⁻¹. The samples were suspended in deionized water (1 mg/ml) and ultrasonicated for 10 min. The suspension was deposited on a small piece of silicon wafer and dried.

Electrochemical measurements for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. The electrochemical characterization by means of linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was performed using an Autolab PGSTAT 204 (Metrohm, Switzerland). A standard three-compartment electrochemical cell was used equipped with an RDE with a glassy carbon disk (geometric surface area: 0.196 cm²) as a working electrode, graphite rod as a counter-electrode, and Hg/HgSO₄ (0.5 M K₂SO₄) as reference electrode. HER LSV measurements were performed in N₂-saturated aqueous 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution at room temperature. For preparing the catalyst ink, catalytic powder (4.0 mg) was dissolved in a

mixture (1 mL) of deionized water, isopropanol, and 5% Nafion (v/v/v = 4:1:0.02) followed by sonication for 30 min before use. The working electrode was polished with alumina suspension, washed with deionized water, and finally sonicated in double-distilled water before casting 8.5 μL aliquots of the electrocatalytic ink on the electrode's surface. Finally, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were acquired from 10^5 to 10^{-1} Hz with an AC amplitude of 0.01 V.

Electrochemical Energy Storage Testing. The slurries were composed of 80 wt.% active material (WSe_2 , $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene and w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ hybrid), 10 wt% polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) as the binder, and 10 wt% carbon black (CB) as the conductive additive. These components were thoroughly dispersed in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), which was used as the solvent. To ensure uniform dispersion, the slurry mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature before being used for electrode fabrication. The slurry was cast onto planar copper (Cu) foil (7 μm thickness), which served as the current collector. A doctor blade set at a height of 250 μm was employed to ensure uniform coating of the slurry on the Cu foil. The coated electrodes were dried in a vacuum oven at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 hours to remove residual solvent. The dried electrodes were then cut into circular discs and stored in an argon-filled glovebox to prevent exposure to moisture or oxygen before cell assembly. The electrochemical performance of the prepared anodes was evaluated using a two-electrode CR2032 coin cell configuration with metallic lithium (Li) as the counter and reference electrode. The electrolyte consisted of 1 M LiPF_6 dissolved in a mixture of ethylene carbonate (EC), diethyl carbonate (DEC), and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (1:1:1 by volume), with 1 wt% vinylene carbonate (VC) added as a stabilizing agent. The cells were assembled in an argon atmosphere, ensuring minimal contamination, and subjected to electrochemical performance testing using a Neware battery testing system. Galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling was performed within a voltage window of 0.001–3.0 V vs. Li^+/Li . An initial current density of 50 mA g^{-1} was used to evaluate the specific capacities of the anode materials. The rate capability was assessed by cycling the electrodes under varying current densities of 25, 50, 100, 200, and 400 mA g^{-1} , with each current density being maintained for five consecutive cycles.

Electrochemical sensing. Measurements were carried out in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer saline (PBS) at pH 7 under ambient conditions, using a 4-channel potentiostat in a three-electrode

electrochemical cell. Glassy carbon (GC) electrode was modified with a 10 μL aliquote of 5 mg ml^{-1} ethanolic suspension of the $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$, dried under ambient conditions and served as working electrode. Pt foil served as a counter electrode and Ag/AgCl , 3M KCl served as a reference electrode. The GC electrode, prior to every use, was carefully polished with alumina slurry on a polishing pad until a mirror finish was obtained, sonicated in ethanol/water for 7 min, and rinsed thoroughly with distilled water.

CV was measured in a potential range from 0.2 to -0.4 V in the presence of 5 mM H_2O_2 at a scan rate of 25 mV s^{-1} . Amperometry experiments were conducted in stirred (150 rpm) solutions at a polarization potential of -0.3 V, except stated otherwise.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.3 Synthesis of Cl-terminated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene

XRD patterns of the synthesized $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene obtained with varying ratios of KCl and CdCl_2 (1:6:2, 1:5:3, 1:3:5, and 1:2:6) are presented in Figure 1a, with the pristine T_3AlC_2 MAX phase included for comparison. The T_3AlC_2 MAX phase exhibits characteristic diffraction peaks at 9.52° , 19.11° , and 38.76° 2θ values, typical of its well-defined layered structure (PDF 04-012-0632).

When different ratios of CdCl_2 and KCl are employed at 700°C for 24 h, notable changes in the diffraction patterns (Figure 1a) are observed. For samples prepared with MAX phase: CdCl_2 : KCl ratios of 1:6:2, 1:5:3, and 1:3:5, a clear shift of the (002) and (004) diffraction peak positions to lower 2θ values is evident, as indicated by the dotted lines in Figure 1a, confirming the successful removal of the Al layer and the synthesis of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. For example, in the MXene synthesized with the ratio 1:3:5, the (002) and (004) diffractions are measured at 7.96° and 15.98° , respectively. The reactions involved in the synthesis are as follows:

Here, KCl acts as a molten co-solvent, providing stability and homogeneity to facilitate the reaction. After the reaction, residual cadmium metal and other reaction residuals are dissolved in concentrated HCl, and the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene is obtained as a powder. For more details on the synthesis, please see the Experimental section.

These results confirm that the ratios 1:6:2, 1:5:3, and 1:3:5 are favorable for synthesizing Cl-terminated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. Among these, the ratio of 1:3:5 is particularly noteworthy, as it achieves successful MXene synthesis while significantly reducing the amount of toxic CdCl_2 used in the etching process. Notably, at least five parts of KCl are required for effective etching, highlighting the potential for optimizing the CdCl_2 : KCl ratio to achieve safer and more environmentally friendly protocols using the LAMS method without compromising the structural integrity of the MXene. In contrast, the sample synthesized with a 1:2:6 ratio shows no synthesis of MXene, as its XRD pattern retains the characteristic peaks of the T_3AlC_2 MAX phase at 9.49° and 19.08° , indicating incomplete conversion and the presence of other mixed phases.

SEM-EDS characterization was performed for the MXene synthesized with a 1:3:5 ratio to further validate the effectiveness of the optimized ratio. As observed in Figure 1b, the SEM image reveals a typical accordion-like morphology, characteristic of multilayered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes, confirming the successful etching of the corresponding MAX phase. The image demonstrates the well-preserved layered structure of the MXene synthesized with the optimized Ti_3AlC_2 : CdCl_2 : KCl ratio. Additionally, this method enables the synthesis of MXene with Cl terminations, as observed in the EDS elemental mapping in Figure 1c. A uniform distribution of titanium (Ti) and chlorine (Cl) is evident throughout the layered structure, with only minor traces of aluminum (Al) particles present. The uniform distribution of Cl as a surface termination highlights the effectiveness of the 1:3:5 ratio in synthesizing Cl-terminated MXenes. This MXene, synthesized with the 1:3:5 ratio, will be used for the next steps of the study and designated as $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure 1. Characterization of LAMS- $Ti_3C_2Cl_2$ MXenes: (a) XRD patterns of MXenes synthesized with different ratios of MAX phase: $CdCl_2$: KCl . (b) SEM image of $Ti_3C_2Cl_2$ MXene synthesized

with the optimized ratio of 1:3:5 and (c) corresponding elemental mapping of elements. Scale bars in (c) represent 10 μm .

2.2. Synthesis of $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene hybrids

After the successful synthesis of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene, this study proceeded to the synthesis of the hybrid materials of $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene with varying compositions: one with a higher ratio of WSe_2 (designated as w- $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$) and the other with a higher ratio of MXene (designated as m- $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$). The preparation of the hybrid materials was accomplished by employing a straightforward solvothermal reaction, in which WSe_2 was deposited onto MXene through the condensation of tungsten hexacarbonyl and selenium. The morphologies of these hybrids are clearly illustrated in the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images shown in Figure 2. In the sample m- $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (Figure 2a), the SEM image reveals that the MXene serves as a prominent scaffold, providing a layered structure for the in-situ growth of WSe_2 nanoflowers on its surface. The yellow square in Figure 2a highlights the WSe_2 nanostructures onto the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene, confirming the formation of the hybrid material. Conversely, the sample w- $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (Figure 2b), exhibits a morphology dominated by WSe_2 , with the MXene layers embedded within the WSe_2 matrix. The yellow square in Figure 2b marks the presence of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene layers embedded by WSe_2 .

Additionally, the SEM image of pristine WSe_2 (Figure 2c) shows a characteristic flower-like morphology, providing an apparent reference for the WSe_2 structure in the hybrids. Figures S1 and S2 provide further EDS analysis of individual components, confirming the uniform distribution of elements in the hybrids. Table S1 summarizes the quantification of elements (atomic %) determined by SEM/EDS analysis for all the synthesized materials.

Figure. 2 SEM images of (a) m-WS₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂, with the yellow square highlighting WSe₂ onto the Ti₃C₂Cl₂ surface. (b) w-WS₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂, with the yellow square indicating Ti₃C₂Cl₂ embedded within the WSe₂. (c) pristine WSe₂.

XRD and Raman spectroscopy were employed to characterize the hybrid material. The XRD patterns of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene further indicate the successful preparation of the hybrid. Figure 3a displays the reflection signals for the plane reflections corresponding to the hexagonal WSe₂ with a P63/mmc space group (reference JCPDF no. 38-1388).³⁰ WSe₂ shows (002), (100), (103), (105) and (110) peaks. In the hybrid material (002) and (103) peaks are present while (100) and (110) follow a downward shift of 3.2° and 2.7°, respectively signifying increased interlayer distance following hybridizing.²¹ Additionally, peaks at 8.15, 16.16°, 24.34°, 40.89°, 49.02°, and 58.06° originating from the MXene are evident in the hybrid material. All the above, confirm the hybrid's successful formation and the interactions between its constituent components. A similar shift is evident in the Raman spectroscopy results. Intact WSe₂ shows bands at 128, 202, and 236 cm⁻¹, corresponding to J₁, J₂, and J₃, which are characteristic of the metallic 1T octahedral phase of WSe₂ (Figure 3b).³¹ Additionally, the band at 245 cm⁻¹ for WSe₂ results from the overlapping E_{2g} and A_{1g} modes, typical of the 2H phase.³¹ Furthermore, Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibit characteristic vibrations, including the A_{1g}(Ti, C, O) mode at 206.5 cm⁻¹ and broad bands within the 260 and 405 cm⁻¹, attributed to the in-plane (E_g) modes of surface groups attached to Ti atoms.^{32, 33} In the 580–730 cm⁻¹ range, known as the carbon region, a band at 606 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder-like band at 704 cm⁻¹ correspond to Ti (E_g) and C (A_{1g}) vibrations, respectively.^{32, 33} In the hybrid material, bands deriving from both individual components are observed: J₁-J₂ bands are seen deriving from WSe₂ are obvious along with the band at 245 cm⁻¹. In-plane (E_g) mode band was found to shift at 253 cm⁻¹ due to Ti atoms from the MXene, suggesting interaction effects that indicate strong interlayer coupling between WSe₂ and MXene at the interface upon hybridization. Also, small bands at 405–606 cm⁻¹ are evident.²⁵

Figure 3. (a) XRD patterns and (b) Raman spectra for w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene (red), WSe₂ (black) and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene (blue).

The analysis of the hybrid w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ was further complemented by TEM analysis. Figures 4a and S3 display TEM images of the hybrid, confirming the presence of WSe₂ nanosheets consistent with SEM observations (Figure 2b). The TEM imaging highlights the flower-like morphology of the WSe₂ nanostructures, formed by interconnected crystalline nanosheets. The spatial distribution of elements within the hybrid is shown through STEM-EDS mapping, revealing the integration of Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene within the WS₂ nanosheets (Figure 4b). In line with the SEM image of the w-WS₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ (Figure 2b), WSe₂ dominates the structure in the hybrid, consistent with its higher ratio in the composition. The EDS mapping (Figure 3b) confirms the presence and distribution of Ti and Cl elements from the MXene, further supporting the synthesis of the hybrid.

Additionally, the TEM image of pristine WSe₂ (Figure 4c) highlights its characteristic morphology, and the elemental mapping (Figure 4d) confirms the uniform distribution of W and Se in the nanosheets. The structural and compositional features of Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene are presented in Figure 4e, which illustrates its characteristic layered morphology consistent with the SEM (Figure 1b). The elemental mapping (Figure 4f) shows a uniform distribution of Ti and Cl, another evidence of the Cl-terminated MXene. TEM analysis of both the hybrid and starting materials (WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂) aligns well with the SEM-EDS results, providing further evidence of the synthesis of the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid by the proposed solvothermal method.

Figure 4. TEM characterization of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid and starting materials: (a) TEM image of the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid with corresponding EDS elemental maps showing the distribution of W, Se, Ti, and Cl elements; (b) TEM image of WSe₂, with corresponding EDS elemental maps showing the uniform distribution of W and Se; (c) TEM image of Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene, with corresponding EDS elemental maps showing the uniform distribution of Ti and Cl. Scale bars for (b) represent 500 nm. Scale bars for (b) and (c) represent 250 nm.

3.3. WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrids as electrocatalysts for HER

Next, the efficacy of both WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ electrocatalysts and reference materials WSe₂, Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene, and Pt/C (20 wt.%) for HER was assessed through LSV in an aqueous 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte (Figure 4). The hybrid with the higher amount of WSe₂ exhibits excellent electrocatalytic activity, indeed much higher compared to that with the lower amount of WSe₂ (Figure 4a). w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ starts the production of hydrogen bubbles at -0.14 V vs RHE, 70 and 110 mV lower compared to pristine Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene and WSe₂, respectively. At the benchmark potential of -10 mA cm⁻², the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid presents an overpotential of just 190 mV, i.e., at -0.19 V vs RHE, 160 mV lower than the m-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ and only 159 mV higher than Pt/C. On the contrary, bare Ti₃C₂Cl₂ and WSe₂ show much higher overpotentials of 400 and 446 mV, respectively.

Figure 4. (a) iR -corrected LSVs for HER obtained at 1600 rpm rotation speed and 5 mV s^{-1} scan rate before (solid lines) and after 10,000 cycles (dashed lines) in aqueous $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$, (b) Tafel

slopes, and (c) Nyquist plots for w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ (red), m-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ (pink), Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene (blue), WSe₂ (black) and Pt/C (20 wt.%) (grey).

The reaction mechanism was analyzed by the extracted Tafel slopes from the LSV curves and by performing Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) as seen in Figures 4b and 4c, respectively. Consistent to the LSV results, w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibited the lowest Tafel slope value of 50 mV/dec suggesting that the rate-determining step is the Heyrovsky step. Here, protons undergo initial adsorb onto the electrode surface through a reduction process (Volmer step), followed by molecular H₂ generation, where hydrogen atoms desorb from the electrode (Heyrovsky step). Conversely, m-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂, along with pristine WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂, displayed higher Tafel slopes of 144, 186, and 112 mV/dec, respectively, indicating slower reaction kinetics due to proton adsorption. EIS results further support the above findings. Conducted at a potential corresponding to -2 mA cm^{-2} and fitted to a Randles circuit, Nyquist plots showed that w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ had the lowest charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) at 18.6 Ω , significantly lower than the R_{ct} m-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ (141.1 Ω), underscoring the former's superior conductivity. Pristine WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene showed higher R_{ct} values of 74.6 and 177.5 Ω , respectively, indicating slower kinetics. The enhanced reaction kinetics of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂, corroborated by Tafel and EIS data, can be attributed to the direct contact enabled by the robust deposition of WSe₂ onto Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene, facilitating efficient electron transfer within the hybrid structure. Additionally, the abundant flower-like WSe₂ in the hybrid provides a high surface area with more exposed active edge sites for enhanced HER performance. Despite pristine Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene having higher HER electrocatalytic activity than pristine WSe₂, its lower intrinsic conductivity limits its efficiency. In the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂, WSe₂'s superior conductivity and abundant active sites contribute to a more effective HER performance than a Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene-rich composition.

The electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) is a crucial parameter for understanding charge transport behavior in hybrid materials. ECSA was determined using the equation: $ECSA = C_{dl}/C_s$, where C_{dl} is the electrochemical double-layer capacitance, and C_s represents the specific capacitance for a flat surface of 1 cm², assumed to be 40 $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for the electrode.¹⁷ To calculate ECSA, cyclic voltammograms of the hybrids, along with WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene, were recorded in a non-Faradaic region at scan rates from 50 to 500 mV s⁻¹ (Figure S4). The w-

WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid achieved the highest ECSA value of around 21.7 cm², followed by m-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid with 9.0 cm². In comparison, WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene showed lower values of approximately 3.6 and 3.1 cm², respectively. These findings align with overall electrocatalytic observations, as w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibits abundant active sites and a larger surface area due to the higher presence of WSe₂. Higher ECSA values reflect a greater active surface area of catalytic sites, which is directly linked to improved electrocatalytic performance.

Finally, the stability of both hybrids and the pristine materials was examined by successive scanning of 10,000 electrocatalytic cycles, as presented in Figure 4a. Notably, both hybrids exhibited a minimal potential loss of only 20 mV, while WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ showed a larger overpotential of 40-50 mV. These results consequently point out the stability of WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrids and, in this regard, their potential for long-time applications in demanding electrochemical processes where stability is an important issue for practical use. All tested parameters for HER are summarized in Table S2.

After evaluating the HER performance of all hybrid compositions in an N₂-saturated aqueous 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte, the hybrid with the optimal WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene ratio, i.e. with higher WSe₂ content, was identified as the best-performing material due to its high electrocatalytic activity.

Having identified the optimized hybrid, we proceeded to evaluate its potential for additional energy-related and electrochemical applications. Applications like HER, LIBs, and electrochemical sensing rely on efficient electron transfer, high catalytic activity, and structural stability, all of which are intrinsic to the hybrid's design. Specifically, the strong electrocatalytic activity and enhanced electron transfer properties of the optimized hybrid made it a promising candidate for both energy storage as an anode material in LIBs and electrochemical sensing for the amperometric determination of H₂O₂.

3.4 w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene hybrid as an anode for LIBs

The electrochemical performance of the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid and bare WSe₂ was evaluated to explore their lithium-ion storage capabilities. The lithiation of TMDs, such as WS₂, MoS₂, and WSe₂, typically involves a two-step intercalation-conversion mechanism.³⁴ During lithiation, Li⁺ ions intercalate into WSe₂ to form an intermediary Li_xWSe₂ phase, which undergoes a conversion

reaction to yield lithium selenide (Li_2Se) and elemental tungsten (W) embedded in the matrix. Conversely, during delithiation, Li_2Se and W recombine to regenerate the Li_xWSe_2 structure, from which Li^+ ions are deintercalated. Galvanostatic charge/discharge tests revealed significant differences in the electrochemical behaviors of the w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ hybrid and bare WSe_2 . Voltage profiles, recorded at 50 mA g^{-1} within a voltage range of 0.001–3.0 V vs. Li^+/Li , showed that bare WSe_2 (Figure 5b) lacked discernible plateaus or kinks, reflecting poor lithiation/delithiation behavior. Similarly, no prominent lithiation/delithiation peaks were observed for the w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ hybrid (Figure 5c), indicating that its capacity predominantly arises from pseudocapacitive contributions driven by rapid surface reactions involving the W redox couple. While bare WSe_2 exhibited an initial discharge capacity of 661 mAh g^{-1} , declining to 240 mAh g^{-1} after 20 cycles, the w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ hybrid demonstrated a five times greater initial discharge capacity of 1255 mAh g^{-1} . It also retained a similar discharge capacity to WSe_2 of 244 mAh g^{-1} after 20 cycles (Figure 5d). Additionally, intact $\text{Ti}_3\text{T}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene shows an initial discharge capacity of 394 mAh g^{-1} , which is more than three times lower than that of the hybrid material (Figure S4a). Its cycling performance is also twice as low (Figures 5a and d).

The rate capability of the hybrid, evaluated under current densities ranging from 25 to 400 mA g^{-1} (Figure 5e), further demonstrated its advantage, achieving specific capacities of 903, 839, 340, 123, and 50 mAh g^{-1} at 25, 50, 100, 200, and 400 mA g^{-1} , respectively, compared to the notably lower performance of bare WSe_2 . The significant enhancement in rate and cycling performance can be attributed to two primary factors: (1) the immediate contact between WSe_2 grown onto the $\text{Ti}_3\text{T}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene matrix, enables charge transfer increasing conductivity within w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$, and (2) the unique flower-like morphology of WSe_2 nanostructures, formed by interconnected crystal nanosheets providing better mechanical stability. This architecture ensures the uniform growth of few-layered WSe_2 nanoflowers on $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene, effectively accommodating volume changes during lithiation/delithiation and preventing mechanical degradation. The integration of WSe_2 onto w- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene improves electrical conductivity and structural stability, resulting in a commendable electrochemical performance, as evidenced by good rate capability, relatively high initial capacity, and moderate cycling retention. These findings underscore the w- $\text{WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ hybrid's potential as a promising anode material for advanced lithium-ion batteries.

Figure 5. Electrochemical evaluation of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid, WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene in the lithium coin cells: (a) Charge/discharge curves of Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene at 50 mA g⁻¹. (b) Charge/discharge curves of WSe₂ at 50 mA g⁻¹. (c) Charge/discharge curves of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid at 50 mA g⁻¹. (d) Cycling performance comparison of Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene, WSe₂ and w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ at 50 mA g⁻¹. (e) Rate performance comparison of WSe₂ and the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ under various current densities.

2.5. w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid as sensor for H₂O₂

The sensing features of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ were investigated and compared with the pristine materials by assessing their electrocatalytic activity towards the reduction of H₂O₂ through CV in the presence of 5 mM in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7) over the potential range from 0.2 to -0.4 V at a scan rate of 25 mV s⁻¹. Results presented in Figure 6a-d reveal that plain GC shows no response upon the addition of H₂O₂ while the Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene demonstrates only a negligible current response. On the other hand, both WSe₂ and w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibit a significant increase in cathodic current upon the addition of H₂O₂, with the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid displaying nearly double the performance of WSe₂ alone. This is clear evidence that the immediate contact between WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene within the hybrid material imparts superior electrocatalytic activity for H₂O₂ reduction, highlighting its capability for enhanced sensing features of this hybrid material.

To this end, the sensing capabilities of w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ were explored using the chronoamperometric technique, correlating the observed catalytic currents with the added concentration of H₂O₂. Aiming to optimize the sensor's experimental conditions we investigated its behavior at different values of polarization potentials from -0.2 to -0.4V over a concentration range of 10-100 μM. The amperometric curves in Figure 6e show that higher potential values increase the current response, while it can affect the stability of the signal. Even though -0.4V offers higher current responses upon the addition of H₂O₂, it lacks stability and linearity over the selected concentration range. Balancing the need for the highest possible analyte signal with the lowest potential value and given the comparable performance of the sensor at -0.35 V and -0.30 V, the latter was chosen as the optimal polarization potential.

Later on, the calibration features of the w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ modified GC were assessed through chronoamperometry at an applied potential of -0.3 V. Figure 6f demonstrates the amperometric curve occurred in the presence of H₂O₂ over the concentration range of 1-88 μM. The cathodic current attributed to H₂O₂ addition is linearly correlated with the tested concentration range of H₂O₂ (Figure 6f inset) with the data fitting the equation $i_p (\mu A) = -0.0213[H_2O_2] (\mu M) - 0.0049$ ($R^2=0.9957$). The limit of detection (LOD), calculated as $3\sigma/slope$, was found to be 0.6 μM.

Figure 6. Cyclic voltammograms of (a) plain GC, (b) $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ MXene/GC, (c) WSe_2/GC and (d) $w\text{-WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{GC}$ in 0.1 M PBS (pH 7) in the presence of 5 mM H_2O_2 at a scan rate of 25 mV s^{-1} . (e) Amperometric curves of $w\text{-WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{GC}$ recorded at different polarization potentials with the corresponding calibration plots. (f) Amperometric curve at -0.3 V in a concentration range $1\text{-}88 \mu\text{M}$ of H_2O_2 along with the corresponding calibration plot. (g) Amperometric curves recorded at -0.3 V with similarly prepared sensors over three consecutive additions of $5 \mu\text{M}$ H_2O_2 along with current response for every H_2O_2 addition.

The $w\text{-WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{GC}$ analytical figures-of merit compare favorably with most of the reported electrochemical sensors for H_2O_2 based on 2D structured materials (Table S3) in terms of LOD and limit of quantification (LOQ). These features in combination with the relatively low polarization potential along with the absence of the need for any deaeration steps in the working solution, render $w\text{-WSe}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_2$ a highly performing sensing electrocatalyst for H_2O_2 .

The reproducibility of the developed sensor was evaluated over five similarly prepared electrodes by addressing the catalytic current stemming from three consecutive additions of $5 \mu\text{M}$ H_2O_2 . Figure 6g illustrates the amperometric curves of the five sensors along with the current response for each of the H_2O_2 additions (Figure 6g inset). Each one of the three additions in the same sensor causes a -small but dissimilar- dilution to the working solution, resulting in a slightly different concentration of H_2O_2 . Considering that, the interelectrode relative standard deviation (RSD) was

calculated for the three H₂O₂ additions separately, and found to be 7.74%, 8.49% and 7.87% for the first, second and third addition, respectively. These values are deemed more than satisfactory and highlight that applying w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ on a GC, leads to sensors with fairly good reproducibility over consecutive measurements.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Developing efficient multifunctional materials is essential for tackling energy challenges, environmental safety and public health concerns. Beyond good performance, a facile fabrication approach is highly desirable. In this context, we developed a hybrid material comprising WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂Cl₂ MXene using a simple solvothermal method, enabling the in-situ growth of WSe₂ nanoflowers onto Ti₃C₂T₂ MXene. The hybrid with a higher WSe₂ content, exhibited outstanding HER electrocatalytic performance, achieving a low overpotential of just 190 mV at -10 mA cm^{-2} . The strong electronic interaction between WSe₂ and Ti₃C₂T₂, facilitated by in-situ growth, significantly enhances charge transfer and accelerates reaction kinetics, leading to high HER electrocatalytic activity. Additionally, w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂T₂ demonstrated excellent stability, with only a slight increase in overpotential after 10,000 cycles. After optimizing the WSe₂-to-MXene ratio for HER performance in acidic conditions, we explored its potential in other applications. As an anode material for Li-ion batteries, w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ exhibited a significantly higher initial discharge capacity of 1255 mAh g⁻¹ nearly twice that of WSe₂ (661 mAh g⁻¹) and more than three times that of Ti₃C₂T₂ (394 mAh g⁻¹). It also demonstrated enhanced rate capability and cycling stability. This improvement is attributed to the hybrid's efficient architecture, which promotes charge transfer and conductivity, while the flower-like morphology of WSe₂ accommodates volume changes during lithiation/delithiation, preventing mechanical degradation. Furthermore, the hybrid's architecture—through the direct contact between its components—offers enhanced sensing capabilities. The w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid demonstrated superior electrocatalytic activity for H₂O₂ reduction compared to WSe₂ alone. The optimized w-WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂/GC sensor achieved a remarkable sensitivity, with a LOD of 0.6 μM, along with excellent reproducibility, positioning it as a promising electrocatalyst for H₂O₂ sensing. Overall, the development of easily fabricated but highly effective nanomaterials is vital for electrochemical applications, where properties like conductivity, stability, and catalytic activity are essential for promoting electron transfer,

electrocatalytic reactions, and energy storage. These insights highlight the promise of the WSe₂/Ti₃C₂Cl₂ hybrid as an excellent option for energy-related and sensing applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research leading to these results was supported by the the Johannes Amos Comenius Programme, European Structural and Investment Funds, project 'CHEMFELLS VI' (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_010/0008122) from the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS). Anastasios V. Papavasileiou was supported by the Onassis foundation - Scholarship ID: F ZS 045–1/2022–2023 and Bodossaki foundation Scholarship. FMO thanks the support from Czech Science Foundation (GA ĀR 25-16769S).

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14866130>

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Graphical abstract

Max-Normalized Radar Chart

